

Linking data and publications: data citation and publication by the NERC data centres

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Historically speaking...

... data was hard to capture, but could be (relatively) easily published in image or table format.

Data and publication were parts of the same thing.

Tried to keep this link through the use of supplementary files for data.

But now...

there's simply too much information associated with everything we need to know about a scientific event.

Journals really don't want to get into the data centre business.

Data always has been the foundation of scientific progress – without it, we can't test any of our assertions, or reproduce our findings!

Suber cells and mimosa leaves. Robert Hooke, Micrographia, 1665

The Data Deluge

“the amount of data generated worldwide...is growing by 58% per year; in 2010 the world generated 1250 billion gigabytes of data”

The Digital Universe Decade – Are You Ready?
IDCC White Paper, May 2010

A lot of people are creating a lot of data, and we're only going to get more of it.

If this is a data deluge – time to start building arks!

Figure 1: The Digital Universe 2009 – 2020
Growing by a Factor of 44

*Zettabyte = 1 trillion gigabytes

Will sharing our data help?

Benefits of sharing:

- Ability to discover and reuse data which has already been collected
- Avoid redundant data collection
- Save time and money
- Provide opportunities for collaboration.

Research funders are keen to encourage data sharing.

For the most part, scientists are happy to share other scientists' data, but...

Knowledge is power!

Data may mean the difference between getting a grant and not.

There is (currently) no universally accepted mechanism for data creators to obtain academic credit for their dataset creation efforts.

And no practical, commonly used ways of linking data to publications.

Creators (understandably) prefer to hold the data until they have extracted all the possible publication value they can.

This behaviour comes at a cost for the wider scientific community.

Reframing “sharing” as “publication” might encourage scientists to be more open with their data.

Why do we want to cite and publish data?

- Pressure from the UK government to make all data from publicly funded research available to the public for free.
 - Scientists still want to receive attribution and credit for their work
 - General public want to know what the scientists are doing (Climategate...)
- Research funders want reassurance that they're getting value for money from their funding
 - Relies on peer-review of science publications (well established) and data (not done yet!)
- Allows the wider research community to find and use datasets outside their immediate domain, confident that the data is of reasonable quality
- From a strict data-centric point of view, citation and publication provides an extra incentive for scientists to submit their data to us in appropriate formats and with full metadata!

CLADDIER

CITATION, LOCATION, And DEPOSITION IN DISCIPLINE &
INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES (CLADDIER)
<http://claddier.badc.ac.uk/trac>

“The result will be a step on the road to a situation where active environmental scientists will be able to move seamlessly from information discovery (location), through acquisition to deposition of new material, with all the digital objects correctly identified and cited.”

Produced a method for writing the citation of a dataset, equivalent to how one would cite a journal paper

e.g. Iwi, A. and B.N. Lawrence. A 500 year control run of HadCM3. [GridSeries, <http://ndg.nerc.ac.uk/csml2/GridSeries>] British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2004. urn: badc.nerc.ac.uk__coapec500yr. fid:jaekfxy [Available from <http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/coapec500yr>].

Did a lot of thinking about the roles, terminology, processes etc involved in data publication

Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)

General Info

Title:	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)	
Type:	Data Entity	
Sub-Type:	Measurement	
Abbreviation:	Chilbolton (CFARR)	
Publication State:	published	
URI:	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_chobs	

Summary

Data from observations made using Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR). The Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) facility at Chilbolton Observatory, Hampshire (51.1445N, 1.4270W) is the home of many observation systems for meteorological and atmospheric science research. There are 4 radar systems designed to study precipitation, clouds and clear air, of which the largest is the 3 GHz Doppler radar (CAMRa) on the 25 m dish. Their wide range of meteorological and multiple raingauge data are available from 1 and liquid water measurements) and downwelling infra-red and visible detect South Wonston to Sparsholt. Cloud camera data from the Chilbolton site are Science and Technology Department of the STFC.

Content

Introduction

The Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR) is a group is also a leading radio science research laboratory. The combination of meas

Please read the 00README file available under the /badc/chilbolton/ directory to guide you through the tree structure and the data directory.

 Documentation and Links to further information and references

Information on updates and changes to the archive is available on the [status page](#).

Documentation is available at the BADC for data for these instruments :

- [94 GHz Galileo radar](#).
- [905 nm Vaisala CT75K lidar ceilometer](#).
- [355 nm UV Raman lidar](#).
- [3 GHz Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological Radar \(CAMRa\)](#).
- [Chilbolton cloud camera](#).
- [Chilbolton disdrometers](#).
- [Chilbolton meteorological sensors](#).
- [Drop-counting and tipping bucket raingauges.v](#)
- [South Wonston to Sparsholt 5 km Radio Links](#).
- [Chilbolton Global Broadcast System](#)
- [Visible and IR radiometers](#).
- [Water vapour profiling radiometer.v](#)
- [winter 1998-99 datasets](#).

Programs are available to users which allow the data to be accessed from IDL, Matlab or PV-Wave. These are described in detail in the [software](#) document.

The [Chilbolton web site](#) provides further information on the facility and the [Chilbolton Weather Web](#) displays live data from the instruments. Details of the work of the Reading University Radar Meteorology group can be found [here](#). A list of [CFARR publications \(2002-2007\)](#) is also available.

 Citation

Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Wrench, C.L.]. Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR) data, [Internet]. NCAS British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-. *Date of citation*. Available from http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_chobs.

 Who to contact

General queries about these pages and access to the available data should be directed to the [BADC Support line](#). Your query should be answered within one working day. When follow-up work is required, the BADC support will carry out the work as quickly and efficiently as possible, and in any case, the user will be kept informed of progress.

Any queries relating to specifics of the data themselves can be directed to [C. L. Wrench](#) of the Chilbolton Group of the STFC.

Overlay Journal Infrastructure for Meteorological Sciences <http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/ojims>

- Created overlay journal mechanics
- Created an open access subject based repository for Meteorology and atmospheric sciences.
- Constructed and evaluated business models for potential overlay journals.

Produced a demonstration data journal, which used overlay mechanics to create data description documents describing a dataset. Didn't go in depth into the mechanics of linking (used URIs)

Did a lot more thinking about the roles, terminology, processes etc involved in data publication

Data Citation and Publication Project Aims

- To implement publication and citation of datasets held within the NERC data centres.
- To increase NERC's influence on work to provide and cite data outputs from scientific work in similar ways to scientific papers.
- To demonstrate to the NERC community that data citation and publication is both personally and scientifically advantageous.
- To form partnerships with other organisations with the same goal of data publication to exploit common activities and achieve a wider community buy-in. To this end, project team members are involved with both the SCOR/IODE/MBL WHOI Library Data Publication Working Group, the CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practises and the DataCite Working Group on Criteria for Datacentres.

- **Provide a reward to scientists who create data for all their efforts in putting their data in one of our data centres.**

The Not-So-Secret life of a PI.

“Publishing” versus “publishing” and “Open” versus “Closed”

We draw a clear distinction between:

publishing/serving = making available for consumption (e.g. on the web), and

Publishing = publishing after some formal process which adds value for the consumer:

- e.g. PloS ONE type review, or
- EGU journal type public review, or
- More traditional peer review.

AND

- provides commitment to persistence

Published

↑

Not Published

We want to:

Encourage scientists to move away from storing their data on CDs in their locked filing cabinets...
....or on hard disks with no backups....

And get them to put their data in a place where it'll be archived and looked after for the future properly.

So why data centres? Can't we just put everything in the cloud? Or on a webpage?

By David Fletcher
<http://www.cloudtweaks.com/2011/05/the-lighter-side-of-the-cloud-data-transfer/>

- Will you be able to find it again?
- How do you know it hasn't changed?
- How can someone else trust it?

“publishing” on the web

To a scientist, there is little benefit from making their dataset available as a free download from a webpage.

Reputational risk of doing so:

- others might find errors, or
- take advantage of the dataset to earn new research funding

Even when sharing is mandated, there are simple ways of stopping people from using data openly posted on-line (e.g. incomprehensible filenames...)

There’s extra effort involved in preparing a dataset for use by others.

Data centres know this extra work is needed, and we want to make sure the dataset author gets credit!

How we're going to cite (and publish) data

We use digital object identifiers (DOIs) as part of our dataset citation because:

- They are actionable, interoperable, persistent links for (digital) objects
- Scientists are already used to citing papers using DOIs (and they trust them)
- There are moves by academic journal publishers (e.g. Nature) to require data sets to be cited in a stable way, i.e. using DOIs.
- The British Library and DataCite gave us an allocation of 500 DOIs to assign to datasets (we got to define what a dataset is).

The screenshot shows the homepage of the DOI System. The header includes the DOI logo, the text 'The DOI® System', and 'Developed by The International DOI Foundation (IDF)'. Navigation links for 'Search Guidelines', 'Contact Us', and 'Members Only' are visible. A 'Site Search' box is on the left. The main content area features a 'Welcome to the DOI® System' section with introductory text about the system's purpose and management. Below this is an 'In the News' section with several news links. At the bottom, there is a 'Resolve a DOI Name' section with a text input field and a 'Submit' button. The footer contains copyright information and a 'Privacy Policy' link.

What sort of data can we/will we cite?

Dataset has to be:

- Stable (i.e. not going to be modified)
- Complete (i.e. not going to be updated)
- Permanent – by assigning a DOI we're committing to make the dataset available for posterity
- Good quality – by assigning a DOI we're giving it our data centre stamp of approval, saying that it's complete and all the metadata is available

When a dataset is cited that means:

- There will be bitwise fixity
- With no additions or deletions of files
- No changes to the directory structure in the dataset "bundle"

A DOI should point to a *html* representation of some record which describes a *data object* – i.e. a landing page.

Upgrades to versions of data formats will result in new editions of datasets.

Centre for Environmental Data Archival
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Search for: in: CEDA NERC Data Catalogue Service

Data from GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site

Record Status: Dataset is Citable
additional metadata fields may be added
Available: 2007-09-20

Download & Services

Data directory for GBS data from Sparsholt: [download](#)

Apply for Access

Help

Geographical Extent

Data Start Date: 2003-10-08
Data End Date: 2005-03-31
Date Update Frequency: notPlanned

Citation

Science and Technology Facilities Council; Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research; Walden, C. J.; Agnew, J.; Waight, J.; Ventouras, S.; Callaghan, S. A., (2007). Data from GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site. NERC - British Atmospheric Data Centre: 10.5285/EBF43A51-0198-4323-A926-FE69225057DD. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5285/EBF43A51-0198-4323-A926-FE69225057DD>

Previous Identifiers Used:

Keywords

Meteorological geographical features

Description

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2005 with signal attenuation sampled once per second. Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras]. GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site. [Internet]. British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-2005. 1st April 2011. doi:10.5285/EBF43A51-0198-4323-A926-FE69225057DD

Project Abstract

Additional Information

Archive content details | Data Lineage

For further details see the following links:

- [CEDA MOLES2 Metadata Catalogue Entry](#)

A short digression: Citation vs. referencing

- Citation – data centre commitment regarding fixity, stability, permanence etc. of a dataset. Demonstrated by assignment of DOI
 - e.g. Darwin, Charles Robert. The Origin of Species. Vol. XI. The Harvard Classics. New York: P.F. Collier & Son, 1909–14;
- Referencing – no data centre commitment regarding fixity, stability, permanence etc. of a dataset. Dataset can still be referenced by URL – but link might be broken
 - e.g. Paragraph 3, page 42, Darwin, Charles Robert. The Origin of Species, 1859
- We want to be able to reference the individual part of the dataset (word/line/paragraph) without having to commit to assigning a DOI to everything in the dataset (book)
- If the dataset is properly frozen, then the reference to a part of it should work fine.
 - Bloggs, Jane and Doe, John, Years 2001, 2005 and 2009 from “Our really important measurements of birds in our garden, 2000-2010”
doi:10.12345/abcdefg.
- And just because someone can (and will) reference something in a dataset that’s not DOI-ready – this act should not trigger a DOI-citation

What data centres can do and what we can't

Publishing data for the scholarly record

- Scientific journal publication mainly focuses on the analysis, interpretation and conclusions drawn from a given dataset.
- Examining the raw data that forms the dataset is more difficult, as datasets are usually stored in digital media, in a variety of (proprietary or non-standard) formats.
- Peer-review is generally only applied to the methodology and final conclusions of a piece of work, and not the underlying data itself. But if the conclusions are to stand, the data must be of good quality.
- A process of data publication, involving peer-review of datasets would be of benefit to many sectors of the academic community.

Most scientists regarded the new streamlined peer-review process as 'quite an improvement.'

<http://libguides.luc.edu/content.php?pid=5464&sid=164619>

Data journals and scientific publication of data

- Now we can cite our datasets using DOIs, we can give academic credit to those scientists who get cited – making them more likely to give us good quality data to archive.
- Publication – and scientific peer-review – is the next step
- We are working with the Royal Meteorological Society and Wiley-Blackwell and have launched a new data journal this month.
 - *Geoscience Data Journal (GDJ)* is an online-only, Open Access journal, publishing short data papers cross-linked to – and citing – datasets that have been deposited in approved data centres and awarded DOIs.

- Data journals already exist:
- Earth System Science Data (<http://earth-system-science-data.net/>)
- Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems (G3 <http://www.agu.org/journals/gc/>)

DATA: BY THE NUMBERS

- Citing data using DOIs will provide a permanent way of linking data with the publications that use it.
 - Scientists already trust DOIs
- But we're not assigning DOIs to all our data, so we still need a commonly used way of linking between data and publications
 - We can do this with URLs – the technology exists
 - What's difficult is getting researchers to cite/reference/link to data as a routine part of writing their papers

“We share because we do science, not alchemy.”
Jason Priem (Datacite Summer meeting, August 2011)

<http://www.keepcalm-omatic.co.uk/default.aspx#createposter>

Thanks!

Any questions?

Image credit: Borepatch <http://borepatch.blogspot.com/2010/06/its-not-what-you-dont-know-that-hurts.html>